

Questionnaire: Monitoring Progress towards the 95-95-95 HIV Strategy in Tshwane sub-district 1

Target Group: Health Professionals (HTS Counsellors, NIMART Nurses, Doctors, PSS, CHWs, etc.)

Location: Tshwane District Sub-district 1, Gauteng Province

Purpose: To assess field-level implementation of HIV testing, ART initiation, and treatment interruption (Lost to follow).

SECTION A: Professional Profile

1. What is your current job role? (Tick one only)

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> HTS Counsellor | <input type="checkbox"/> NIMART Nurse |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Medical Officer / Doctor | <input type="checkbox"/> Treatment Navigator |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Community Health Worker (CHW) | <input type="checkbox"/> other (please specify): |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Psychosocial Support (PSS) | |

2. How many years of experience do you have working in HIV services?

- 1 Less than 1 year
- 2 1–3 years
- 3 4–6 years
- 4 More than 6 years

3. What type of facility do you work at?

- Clinic
- Community Health Centre

4. Facility name

- Boekenhout CHC
- Boikhutsong Clinic
- Garankuwa View
- ClinicKgabo CHC
- KT Motubatse Clinic
- Maria Rantho
- Phedisong 1 CHC
- Phedisong 4 CHC
- Phedisong 6 Clinic
- Sedilega Clinic
- Soshanguve 2 Clinic
- Soshanguve Block TT Clinic
- Soshanguve Block X Clinic
- Soshanguve CHC
- Tlanelong Clinic
- Winterveld Clinic

SECTION B: HIV testing Coverage

5. Do you think stigma makes it difficult to offer HIV testing?

- Yes
- No

6.. Do you think fear of discrimination makes it difficult to offer HIV testing?

- Yes
- No

7. Do you face a shortage of HIV test kits that makes it difficult to offer testing?

- Yes
- No

8. Do staff shortages make it difficult to offer HIV testing?

- Yes
- No

9. Do patients refusing testing make it difficult to offer HIV testing?

- Yes
- No

10. Are outreach services (e.g., mobile clinics, campaigns) effective in increasing HIV testing uptake?

- Very effective
- somewhat effective
- not effective
- not available

11. Do you receive regular training or updates on HIV guidelines (e.g., UTT, MMD, TLD transition)?

- Regularly
- Occasionally
- Rarely
- Never

SECTION C: ART Initiation

Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements:

12. Patient denial of their HIV-positive status causes delays in starting ART.

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

13. Fear of stigma causes delays in starting ART.

- Strongly Agree
- Agree

- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

14. Fear of disclosure causes delays in starting ART.

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

15. Concerns about side effects cause delays in starting ART.

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

16. Patient not feeling ready causes delays in starting ART.

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

17. Medication stock-outs cause delays in starting ART.

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

18. Long waiting times cause delays in starting ART.

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

19. Lack of counselling space causes delays in starting ART.

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

20. Lack of enough staff causes delays in starting ART.

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

21. Relocation causes delays in starting ART.

- Strongly Agree
- Agree

- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

22. Migration causes delays in starting ART.

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

23. Lack of transport or money causes delays in starting ART.

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

24. Poor support or counselling causes delays in starting ART.

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

25. Does your facility have a formal system in place for tracing patients who interrupt treatment (LTFU)?

- Yes
- No

26. If YES, please indicate which methods your facility uses: choose more than one (checkbox)

- Phone calls to the patient
- SMS reminders
- Home visits by CHWs or outreach teams

END OF QUESTIONNAIRE

Thank you for participating. Your response will be help improve HIV service delivery in Tshwane.